

Section 30.1 and Software Collections: A User's Guide

July 2022

Companion to "Section 108 and Software Collections: A User's Guide"

Graeme Slaght

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	1
Acknowledgments	2
Preservation and Fair Dealing’s Flexibility	3
Eligibility and limitations: 30.1 (1) (a), (c), and 30.1 (2)	5
Eligibility of LAMs: 30.1 (1)	5
Collaborative Collection Management and Maintenance: 30.1 (1)	5
Nature and format of eligible works	6
Copying rare or unpublished works: 30.1(1)(a)	6
Copying for the purposes of in-person consultation: 30.1(1)(b)	6
Copying works into an alternative format: 30.1(1)(c)	7
Limitation: Ambiguity of the Meaning of Commercial Availability in 30.1 (2) and the Act	8
Special Note: Section 41 and Technological Protection Measures (TPMs)	9

Acknowledgments

Thank you to Ana Enriquez, Brandon Butler, Paula Jabloner, Kyle Courtney, Alyssa Loera, Phil Salvador, Ariel Katz, Mark Swartz, Jess Whyte, Lauren Byl, Stephen Marks, and James Plotkin for their helpful feedback and assistance.

This guide was prepared in tandem with [Section 108 and Software Collections: A User's Guide](#) which describes American Law and which is also published by the Software Preservation Network.

License:

This guide is licensed under the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\) License](#).

Preferred citation:

Slaght, G. (2022). Section 30.1 and Software Collections: A User's Guide. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6949215](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6949215)

Like fair dealing (Section 29), [Section 30.1](#) of the Copyright Act, known as the “Management and maintenance of collection” exception, places certain software preservation activities by libraries, archives, and museums (LAMs) outside the scope of copyright. Section 30.1 is similar to fair dealing in that it allows LAMs to engage in software preservation activities without permission from rightsholders.

Unlike fair dealing, which the Supreme Court of Canada has defined as a broad and flexible user’s right that could apply to a wide variety of uses, [see [paragraphs 30-32 of *Theberge*](#) and [paragraph 48 of *CCH*](#)] the rights granted by Section 30.1 apply to preservation activities directly and have statutorily specified eligibility requirements, limitations, and procedures.

Nevertheless, it is important to understand the baseline that Section 30.1 provides to LAMs engaging in the preservation of software. Section 30.1 identifies types of lawful copying that do not require permission from rightsholders. The activities that 30.1 permits do not encompass all copying that may be necessary to preserve and maintain access to software collections, and are subject to limitation. Therefore, it is advisable to read this guide alongside [SPN’s Best Practices for Fair Use in Software Preservation](#), the situations, principles and limitations of which are [transferable into the Canadian context of fair dealing](#).

Preservation and Fair Dealing’s Flexibility

Unlike fair use, fair dealing has a two-step process for determining whether a use can be deemed to qualify for its protections.

Firstly, the conventional wisdom is that section 29 has a finite list of enumerated statutory purposes for which fair dealing can be applied. To qualify as fair dealing, it is generally understood that a use *must* be for one of these purposes before it can be subsequently analyzed for fairness in the multi-factorial second step of a fair dealing analysis.

This list of purposes does not include “preservation,” which may pose some difficulties for some preservation activities that want to rely solely on Section 29. However, the Supreme Court of Canada in *CCH* (paragraph 51) has stated that the meaning of the fair dealing purposes at the first step of the fair dealing test, “must be given a large and liberal interpretation in order to ensure that users’ rights are not unduly constrained.” (This instruction can rightly be applied to all users’ rights in the Act). Furthermore, multiple Supreme Court decisions in recent years have

followed *CCH* and clarified the scope of the rights of intermediaries to reproduce works on behalf of end-users for either direct or anticipated requests (*Alberta v. Access Copyright, SOCAN v. Bell*). For example, In *Alberta*, the court described the relationship between teacher (the intermediary) and student (the end-user) as “symbiotic.” These subsequent cases reiterated that fair dealing applies not only to end-users when they reproduce works for their own purposes but also to intermediaries who reproduce works on end-users’ behalf. While the relationship between a library preserving its software collection and the potential future users of its collection may be less immediately symbiotic than that between a teacher and student, copying in order to be proactive in ensuring future availability and access to works is highly likely to meet the first step of the fair dealing test.

Even if many instances of preservation for the purposes of facilitating an end-user’s research would pass this first step of the fair dealing test, some may argue that preservation for preservation’s sake would not, and that such activities must only rely on Section 30.1. Such a narrowing of fair dealing’s scope is needlessly cautious and would run counter to the Supreme Court of Canada’s instructions . LAMs themselves, even if they aren’t the end-users of the materials they collect, have their own institutional purposes – their contribution to *research* is larger than the mere accounting of each individual research use. As the Supreme Court said at paragraph 49 of *CCH*, “the fair dealing exception is always available. Simply put, a library can always attempt to prove that its dealings with a copyrighted work are fair under s. 29 of the Copyright Act. It is only if a library were unable to make out the fair dealing exception under s. 29 that it would need to turn to ...[a specific library exception] to prove that it qualified for the library exception.” Prior to *CCH*, it could have been argued that since Parliament had enacted a specific exception for preservation, software preservationists could make lawful reproductions for preservation purposes only if they satisfied all the conditions of Section 30.1 with no recourse to Section 29. *CCH* explicitly rejects such an argument. However, as we will see below, section 30.1 does provide important and clear rights for LAMs that qualify under its limitations so that they may engage in robust and lawful preservation activities.

With this guidance from the Court in mind, considering Section 30.1 in tandem with Section 29 best provides the full scope of rights to LAMs that might be considering preservation activities with a clear end-use in mind as well as activities that are highly operational in nature (such as a mass migration of a collection to a new digital location), or are driven by technical, maintenance, or infrastructural concerns. Together, these sections provide a dependable, broad, and flexible basis for software preservation activities by LAMs in Canada.

Eligibility and limitations: 30.1 (1) (a), (c), and 30.1 (2)

Eligibility of LAMs: 30.1 (1)

A library, archive, or museum, or a person acting under the authority of one such institution, qualifies for this exception. Unlike in the case of the eligibility requirements for the equivalent US Section 108, there are no requirements in 30.1 itself that the preserving institution's collection be open to the public or be available to unaffiliated persons.

However, the Copyright Act's **definition of a library, archive, or museum**, does create eligibility considerations for the use of 30.1. To fall under the remit of this exception, a LAM must not be a for-profit institution or must not be administered or controlled by a for-profit entity. As a result, a corporate library or archive would not qualify. The LAM must also be open to the public or to researchers, which is a fairly broad requirement that most if not all LAMs would meet.

Collaborative Collection Management and Maintenance: 30.1 (1)

30.1 permits a qualified LAM to make a copy of a work in its permanent collection not only for the maintenance and management of its collection but also for the management and maintenance of the permanent collection of another qualified LAM.

This is meaningful for software collections, as one institution may hold the software required by another institution for the continued use of software in a collection (such as when the software consists of an application that requires a specific version of an operating system held at another institution). Section 30.1 permits the reproduction of software collections in such a collaborative manner, provided all its other requirements are met.

Nature and format of eligible works

30.1 is focused on the nature of the works under consideration for copying, the character and purpose of the copying itself, and whether an appropriate replacement copy is commercially available.

Three subsections related to the nature of the original work are especially relevant for software preservation activities because they pay particular attention to rare works and format and technological obsolescence: 30.1(1)(a), 30.1(1)(b) and 30.1(1)(c).

Copying rare or unpublished works: 30.1(1)(a)

The first of these is 30.1(1)(a), which stipulates that the exception can apply for works that are:

- (a) Rare or unpublished and;
 - (i) Deteriorating, damaged, or lost, or
 - (ii) At risk of deterioration or becoming damaged or lost

For a qualified LAM, rare but published works of software, particularly those stored on physical or optical media (floppy disks, cd-roms), would fall under the remit of this clause. Rare and unpublished software would also qualify.

Copying for the purposes of in-person consultation: 30.1(1)(b)

A qualified LAM is entitled to make a copy of a work for the purposes of on-site consultation if the original work “cannot be viewed, handled, or listened to because of its condition or because of the atmospheric conditions in which it must be kept.” Copies of works held on physical media that are at risk of deterioration or which already bear the marks of deterioration could be copied and made available on a machine located on the premises of the LAM.

Copying works into an alternative format: 30.1(1)(c)

30.1(1)(c) states that it is not copyright infringement for a qualifying LAM to reproduce a work:

(c) in an alternative format if the library, archive or museum or a person acting under the authority of the library, archive or museum considers that the original is currently in a format that is obsolete or is becoming obsolete, or that the technology required to use the original is unavailable or is becoming unavailable

Taken together these stipulations widen the scope of Section 30.1 to not just allow the reproduction and preservation of works that are rare, unpublished, or at risk of deterioration, but also the reproduction of works into alternative formats if the LAM or person acting under its authority *considers* that the works are currently held in formats that are obsolete or *becoming obsolete*. If a piece of software is in a format that the LAM considers is obsolete or becoming obsolete, the qualifying LAM may copy it into a new format or alternative storage medium that would presumably also allow a means to access the work. The formulation of this subsection is important to read closely; the relevant question it poses is not whether the format is obsolete or becoming obsolete but whether the LAM considers it so. The subsection credits the intermediary role of LAMs in coming to professional conclusions about the lifespan of media formats and to manage their collections accordingly. Even if a professional consideration would turn out to be incorrect (as would be the case if a dead or dying media format were revived by hobbyists) the exception would apply.

30.1(1)(c) goes further by not only referring to format obsolescence, but technological obsolescence more broadly. According to this subsection, if a LAM considers that “the technology required to use the original is unavailable or becoming unavailable,” then it may also reproduce a work into an alternative format which would allow the use of the work. Activities such as mounting or reproducing a piece of software within an emulation of no-longer available technology would be permitted by this subsection, as would the emulation of an operating system, which makes this subclause highly useful for software preservation activities.

Alongside this subsection’s reliance on the professional consideration of LAMs, its language of “becoming obsolete” and “becoming unavailable” also leaves even more room for the professional judgment of staff working in qualifying LAMs to

determine whether a particular work falls within this clause. 30.1 is especially attuned to the fact that digital preservation often or always also must incorporate consideration of software preservation so that a full and faithful reproduction of an original work can be reproduced as it might have appeared to an original user, presently, and in the future.

Limitation: Ambiguity of the Meaning of Commercial Availability in 30.1 (2) and the Act

The section contains a limitation on the affordances of paragraphs (1)(a), (1)(b) and (1)(c) - these paragraphs do not apply if “an appropriate copy is commercially available in a medium and of a quality that is appropriate for the purposes of subsection (1) [the management and maintenance of a permanent collection].”

This raises a problem with the language of 30.1, previously identified by advocates for the work and rights of Canadian LAMs, with respect to determining the existing commercial availability of a given work. The definition of availability in 30.1 does not exactly match the language in the **definition of commercial availability** provided by the Copyright Act at Section 2.

30.1 (2) is clearly about obtaining a commercially available physical or digital copy of a work, not a license for its reproduction. For many works in software collections, this kind of commercial availability is likely no longer present.

However, the Copyright Act’s definition of commercial availability includes not just the case, as described in 30.1, of (a) a commercially available, reasonably priced copy that can be located with reasonable effort, but also (b) a license to reproduce the work from a collective society “within a reasonable time and for a reasonable price and may be located with reasonable effort.”

Software works may in and of themselves be in the repertoire of a collective society, or works compiled within software, such as musical or artistic works, may be as well. Canada has many collective societies which may offer a license pertaining to the reproduction of such works. However, obtaining a license for preservation activities from a collective society is likely not to meet the threshold of reasonableness in most cases. Most collective societies do not offer transactional licenses for single uses, but blanket licenses for all works in their repertoire, which

may not be an appropriate and reasonable option for a single instance of a copy made for the purposes of the management and maintenance of a collection. Conversely, a single-use license may also not be appropriate for such activities, as copying may be necessary at multiple points along the lifecycle of preserved software, and obtaining such a single-use license, if it were actually available, each time a copy were created is likely not a reasonable approach either.

Special Note: Section 41 and Technological Protection Measures (TPMs)

Software preservation practitioners must also take into account Canadian law's expansive prohibitions on circumventing TPMs; these anti-circumvention rules were introduced in 2012 and are notable for their stringency and for the ongoing efforts of the courts and others in Canada to clarify ambiguities in the relationship of these new rules to the overall scheme of the Copyright Act, especially its balancing of users' and creators' rights.

Section 41 of the Copyright Act sets various definitions, prohibitions, and exceptions related to TPMs and circumvention, and at 41.1 (a) establishes a prohibition on the circumvention of access control TPMs, as defined at 41(a). Section 41 is silent on whether this prohibition on circumvention extends to cases in which the work is legally acquired and where reproducing a work may be permissible under an exception in the Act, such as under sections 29 or 30.1. While Section 41 does include a list of carve-outs for other purposes for which these restrictions are removed, such as for making computer programs interoperable, for encryption and security research, and for the provision of accessible materials to persons with perceptual disabilities (41.16(1)), there is no specific subsection that contains an exception for circumvention by the activities of LAMs or for purposes that would otherwise be permitted by another exception to copyright infringement or a user's right (like Sections 29 or 30.1).

There are three other subsections in Section 41 of which LAMs engaging in software preservation should be aware:

At 41.2, the Act states that in the case where a LAM or educational institution was unaware that their activities contravened the prohibition on circumvention, the only remedy available to a rightsholder is an injunction (as opposed to statutory or other damages or remedies). As a result, if a LAM were to inadvertently circumvent a TPM

in its preservation activities, the LAM would not be at risk of financial or criminal penalties and may be simply required to put a stop to its preservation activities with respect to a specific work or works.

At 41.21(2) the Act does refer to the potential impact of the Section on the balance of users' and creators' rights, by describing the possibility that a TPM "could adversely affect criticism, review, news reporting, commentary, parody, satire, teaching, scholarship or research." 41.21(2) enables the government to enact a regulation which might address this problem. Unfortunately, no such regulation has yet been enacted.

And finally at 42 (3.1), the criminal penalties for individuals who are found guilty of the circumvention of TPM are laid out. They are extremely punitive. However, there is an exception to these penalties made for "a person who is acting on behalf of a library, archive or museum or an educational institution." A LAM as an institution may still be liable, however, if the circumvention was performed in full knowledge of its prohibition, i.e. intentionally.

Canada's Federal Court took up Section 41 for the first time in 2017, and its decision in [Nintendo of America v. King](#) further clarified that the 2012 changes had in effect established a statutory damages regime on circumvention for commercial purposes, removing the need for infringement to be proved before such damages can be applied.

Canadian software preservationists, therefore, when planning their projects and services, must take into account the wide-ranging scope of Section 41 and the subsequent affirmation by the Federal Court that it was indeed Parliament's intent to establish a broad and punitive regime related to TPMs. The lack of explicit exceptions in Section 41 for users' rights, or specifically for the rights of LAMs, means that there is a resulting lack of clarity about whether Section 41 does indeed override those rights contained in other sections of the Copyright Act. However, it is also true that Section 41 does not explicitly override these rights either.

Furthermore, some users' rights in the Act, such as the exception for reproduction for private purposes (29.22) do contain explicit limitations that this right applies only if "an individual did not circumvent, as defined in section 41, a technological protection measure." That Sections 29 and 30.1, amongst others, were not amended to also include this limitation suggests that it was not the intent of Parliament to override all users' rights for works for which TPMs are present via Section 41.

Further clarity about the implications of Section 41 on software preservation activities may soon exist. After the statutory review of the Copyright Act in 2018, the Canadian Parliamentary Standing Committee on Industry, Science and Technology (INDU) did admit that the Act's TPM provisions' over-breadness deserved attention by Parliament and in its [Recommendation 19](#) suggested the introduction of further exceptions to TPM anti-circumvention rules "affecting Canadians and Canadian institutions," most notably for the Right to Repair. Unfortunately, this recommendation has yet to be translated into legislative text or regulation. Furthermore, another Federal Court decision in 2016, [Blacklock's Reporter v. Canada](#), found that fair dealing purposes can in some circumstances override an access control TPM (in this case a paywall), suggesting the possibility that a flexible or purposive approach to interpreting this section within the broader framework of the Act will continue as the courts take up a related case involving users' rights and TPMs. That being said, software preservationists should proceed with caution and with hope that the next five-year Parliamentary review of the Copyright Act in 2023 may result in responsive legislative proposals or regulations to fix the glaring ambiguities posed by Section 41 to LAMs' otherwise lawfully broad rights to engage in preservation activities.

